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University Dental College
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Treatment Seeking Behavior on Occupational Health Hazard Among Garment Workers in Dhaka City

Akhtar J¹, Begum F², Qureshi A³, Noor LA⁴, Ahmed A⁵

ABSTRACT:

The aim of this study was to assess the treatment seeking behavior on occupational health hazard of garments workers in Dhaka, Bangladesh; as the garment sector has been playing an important role in creating job opportunity to the rural people. This was a cross sectional descriptive survey among the garment's workers of Flaxen Dress Makers Ltd. at Uttara, Dhaka. Simple random sampling was applied. Data collection was carried out from August, 2015 to January, 2016 by using a semi-structured questionnaire. The sample size of the study was 226. The mean age of the respondents was 25.5 ±5 years. Out of respondents 63.7% were male, 36.3% were female of which 80.5% were married. In terms of education level about 40.3% respondents were found who studied till class eight and 16.45% were primarily educated. 72.1% workers sought modern treatment from hospital when they fell sick or any other injury. From this study we found that, though the workers want to receive modern health care facility, they cannot achieve due to their poor treatment seeking behavior.

Key words: Treatment seeking behavior, occupational health hazard, garments workers.

1. Dr. Jubaida Akhtar
Lecturer, Dept. of Dental Anatomy
University Dental College & Hospital.
2. Prof. Dr. Fahmida Begum
Professor (C.C.) & Head
Department. of Dental Anatomy
University Dental College & Hospital.
3. Dr. Ashik Qureshi
Associate Professor (C.C) & Head(Incharge)
Department of Pediatric Dentistry
University Dental College & Hospital.
4. Dr. Latifa Al Noor
Lecturer
Department of Dental Pharmacology
Dhaka Community Medical College
Hospital & Dental unit.
5. Dr. Anam Ahmed
Associate professor (C.C)
Department of Dental Public Health
University Dental College & Hospital

Address of correspondence:

Dr. Jubaida Akhtar
Lecturer
Department of Dental Anatomy
University Dental College and Hospital.
e-mail: jubaidasa@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION:

The ready-made garment (RMG) sector has played a major role in the development of the economical area in Bangladesh. By late 1980, the readymade garments industry took the lead in earning foreign currency and making a big job market.¹ Now in Bangladesh there are about 3760 of several categories privately owned garment factories that are registered with BGMEA.² In our country RMG sector plays an important role in the overall economic development. Now a days, Bangladesh exports readymade garments to about 30 countries around the world with the majority of production destined for U.S and European markets.¹ As an apparel exporter, Bangladesh now accounts for almost 78% of total exports.³ Employment in the Readymade garment sector in Bangladesh provides workers with economic benefits and some empowerment. The clothing sector is usually running by young, urbanizing workers many of whom are female coming from lower society.⁴ Bangladesh has often received negative impression from the world because the safety & health condition record of our factories is non-acceptable But it should comply with international trade regulations and provide healthy and secure workplaces.² Treatment seeking behavior is now of special importance because sound health is one of

the essential forces for promoting socioeconomic progress in a society.

Treatment seeking behavior refers to the sequences of remedial actions that one can undertake to cure perceived ill health. It is initiated with identification of symptoms, on which a treatment plan is devised.¹ Healthcare will be delivered by the medical professionals such as registered doctors, nurses, physiotherapist and psychiatrist. According to the labor laws of Bangladesh and the standards of the International Labor Organization (ILO), industries must provide health facilities to their workers. But it is very remarkable that most factories do not have any appointed medical doctors or nurses to care for their staffs, even they are not accustomed with any medical program of the government or any private sector. This expresses both improper monitoring and manufacturers' lack of willing to provide proper healthcare facilities for the workers; what are their rights.⁵ As a result, the entire condition of health system for the apparel workers is insufficient and unhealthy in Bangladesh, causing in fall of workers' productivity levels. To improve the health condition of RMG workers in Bangladesh through the provision of general health care services including family planning and maternal and child health (MCH) services, training on basic first aid and development of referral systems along with the facility of antenatal care (ANC)⁶ is necessary. It is also important to develop a basic education department for creation of awareness in personal health and hygiene practices. Loose motion, cough and breathlessness are very common among the clothing workers of our garment sector. Diarrhoea, common cold, asthma and other respiratory tract infection are found as predominant diagnosis. Sewing machine operators and cutters are the ones usually suffering from neck and shoulder pain. Psychiatric disorders in patients with chronic work-related musculoskeletal pain are often found in the garment sector.⁷ As the workers are slum

dwellers, it is easy to become sick with contagious diseases like eczema, scabies, etc. Nevertheless, majority are seeking treatment from local health assistants. In readymade garment sector, it is notable that married women are reluctant to seek treatment due to lack of privacy, want of female doctors and health workers, costly treatment, and their subordinate social status along their ignorance about sound health and sound life.⁸ The hesitation is exacerbated when symptoms are perplexing, as they are with reproductive tract infection (RTI), particularly among the young women. The treatment seeking behavior of women is not as improved as desired.⁸ Unfortunately, they are paid very little, in fact, their pay is among the lowest anywhere in the world. This situation makes the workers very vulnerable to different kinds of health-related problems, including malnutrition and also results in their poor health-care seeking behavior.⁹ Workers usually do not seek treatment for sexual health problem because of their lack of awareness, and insufficient treatment facilities. Moreover, RTI and sexually transmitted infections that are associated with some sort of socio-cultural stigmas. As being a vulnerable group for spreading infectious diseases it is required for creating awareness and delivering proper knowledge to control the sexual health problems including HIV/AIDS among the young people.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This was a descriptive type of cross-sectional study conducted among the garment's workers of Flaxen Dress Makers Ltd. at Uttara, Dhaka between August, 2015 to January, 2016 by using a semi-structured questionnaire. Simple random sampling was applied. Sample size was 226. SPSS version 20, MS-Office etc. windows program was used for proper data analysis and report writing.

RESULTS:

Histogram (Figure-1) shows the distribution of age of the garment’s workers where the highest 8.98% of workers fall in the age group of 18-30 years and only 4% was found in the age group of 41-50 years among the 226 respondents. The mean age of our respondents was 25.5 ±5 years.

Whereas bar diagram (Figure-2) shows the distribution of educational qualification among the interviewed respondents, where considering the level of education, 40.3% had class VIII level of education, about 21.7% had secondary education, 16.4% had primary & higher secondary level of education, 3.1% was graduated & 2.2% was illiterate only. This can be a positive indicator supporting the recent efforts of the government on education.

Moreover Figure-3 expresses majority of the clothing workers (63.3%) had monthly family income from the range of Taka (21,000-30,000)/- followed by (27%) Taka (10,000- 20,000)/- only, the mean monthly family income was BDT 22,827/=

Fig-1 Distribution of respondents according to their age group. Mean age was 25.5 ±5 years.

Fig-3 Distribution of respondents according to their monthly family income. Mean monthly income was BDT 22,827/=

Fig-2 Distribution of respondents according to their educational qualification.

Fig-4 Distribution of garments workers by sources of health service information

Table-1: Distribution of garment workers by types of illness suffered at the time of interview

Illness	Frequency (226)	Percent (%)
No illness	57	25.1
General weakness	32	14.1
Headache	43	18.9
Body ache	24	10.6
Cough	22	09.7
Anorexia	03	01.3
Chest pain	21	09.3
Abdominal pain	11	04.8
Faintness	01	0.4
Others	01	0.4

Table-2: Distribution of treatment seeking behavior by the garment's workers

Treatment type	Frequency (n=226)	Percent (%)
Homeopathy	19	8.4
Kobiraj	04	1.8
Ayurvedic	01	0.4
Local doctor	12	5.3
Treatment from pharmacy	15	6.6
Treatment from hospital	163	71.8
Self-medication	11	04.8

The pie chart (Figure-4) describes the distribution of garments workers by source of health service information. Here we saw the majority of the worker (82.3%) got health service information from television followed by cell phone (11.10%). Next to those internet and radio contributed for health service information.

On other hand table-1 shows different illness that workers were suffering from at the time of their interview. Here, 18.9% were suffering from headache, 14.1% were from general weakness, 10.6% were from body ache, 9.7% were from cough, 9.3% were from chest pain & 4.8% were from abdominal pain. However, 25.1% of them were sound well.

Table-2 explains the treatment seeking behavior of the respondents. Among 226, the majority of the workers (71.8%) sought modern treatment from the hospital on their health care issues. 8.4%, 1.8%, 0.4% were interested to receive treatment from homeopathy, kobiraj & ayurvedic respectively. 6.6% and 5.3% were preferred to take treatment from pharmacy & local doctor respectively. Only 4.8% was like self-medication.

DISCUSSION:

This was a cross-sectional study that was conducted with the aim of determining the treatment seeking behavior on occupational health hazard of garment workers in Dhaka, Bangladesh, they are now playing the key role of country's growing economy and development.

In our study, among 226 respondents, the highest 89.8% was found in the age group of 18-30 years, 6.25% and 4% was found in the age group of 31-40 and 41-50 years respectively. The mean age of the respondents was 25.5±5 years. Considering the level of education, 40.3% studied up to class eight, 21.7% had secondary education, 16.4% had completed higher education and up to primary education each, 3.1% were graduated only and 2.2% were illiterate. In a study done by Md. Golam Hasnain.⁹ showed that, among the 300 participants 43.33% were illiterate, 40% had completed the primary educational level, and only 16.67% had completed the secondary educational level. A little bit different picture was found in the study done by Jahan M.¹⁰ where, 26.6% workers had no formal education but could sign their names, 20% had education at primary level and up to class eight each. The study of Rajat Das Gupta et.al (2015)¹¹, found that among 145 respondents, the mean age was 23.30 year ranging from 11-45 years of age where 45.52% received institutional educations and 15.2% of respondents was illiterate.

In this study, the mean monthly income was US\$ 270.85±57.8. Golam Hasnain⁹ in his study found that the garment workers' average monthly income was \$ 63.20 ± \$ 14.01. Wages in Bangladesh increased to 13258 BDT / Month in 2017 (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, 2016-2017). Per capita income of Bangladesh rose to USD1,751 (Star Online Report, September 18, 2018). In the global garment industry, Bangladeshi workers are paid some of the lowest wages. The current minimum wage of about

US\$ 63 ([https://tradingeconomics.com / bangladesh / wages](https://tradingeconomics.com/bangladesh/wages)). So, the economic status is far below any credible living cost estimate. Garments workers have low education level and low-income level where both play as an obstacle to get proper health service.

Among the participants, the workers who had general weakness 14.1%, headache 18.9%, anorexia 13%, peptic ulcer 45.6% and cough were 10.6%. On examination, 25.1% of the participants had no illness, and no other signs of deficiency disorders were observed. But another study shows that, 79% of the female garment workers had some illness and the major problems were diarrhoea and respiratory tract infection.⁷ Rajat D.G.¹¹ said in his study the prevalence of occupational health hazards was 88.28%. Maximum 51% respondents suffered from headache and shoulder pain. 44.1% respondents had no problem with their working environment.

In our study, the modern treatment-seeking behavior was moderately high. We found about 72.1% respondents interested to take modern medical facilities from hospital when they fell sick or any injury occurred, 8.4% went to homeopathy, 1.8% seek treatment from kobiraj, 0.4% from ayurvedic, 5.3% went to local doctors, 6.6% had treatment from pharmacy and 4.95% took self-medication. Golam Hasnain⁹ showed in his study around 12% of them went to qualified practitioners and 37% completed the prescribed treatment. Aderonke¹² found the most sought-after health-seeking behavior among participants was self-medication 31.4% followed by herbal preparations 17.8%. Only 3.7% (12/325) sought hospital treatment and 2.5% sought hospital treatment in addition to other treatments. None of the factories had a regular doctor and none of the respondents received treatment facilities from the garment authorities. Treatment facility was only provided for major accidents while working in the factories. In the study of Jahan M.¹⁰, the workers of 5 garment factories were deprived of treatment facilities. All the factories had first aid box to take care of minor accidents but there was no regular doctor. Rajat D.G.¹¹ revealed that 84.8% got medical services by constant presence of doctor or, nurses. 78.6% workers received primary treatment and free medication. 48.3% had periodic health checkup, 44.1% had pre-placement

examination. Rahman and Rahman¹ said in their study 56%, 21% & 10% received treatment from LMAF, pharmacists & kobiraj respectively. About 11% respondents had no consultation for their illness. In another study, Akhter S et al¹³ found that 43% did not know about the health treatment facilities, 13% workers were not getting proper medical care, only 44% were getting first aid treatment. This study also examined clothing workers were seeking health information from various sources. The result showed that 82.3%, got information from TV, 2.7% from Radio, 3.5% from internet, 11.1% from cell phone, and 0.4% from newspapers. Amr Jamal¹⁴ found that, among 344, 62.8% got information from their physician, 45.1% from television, 32.8% from family, 29.1% from newspapers, and 27.9% from Internet.

CONCLUSION:

The low educational levels, poor economic status of the garment workers and their ill working environments and exposure to occupational hazards make them vulnerable to certain risks. The lack of knowledge on sound health make the poor workers more vulnerable in terms of affordability and choice of health provider. This study shows that, though they want to take modern health-care facility, they do not achieve due to their poor treatment seeking behavior. So, policy makers and owners should take notice and proactively provide sufficient incentives and awareness programs to help correct the treatment seeking behavior and economic conditions that their workers face. The attitude of the factory owners and worker's satisfaction with the treatment play a role in health seeking behavior.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

There is needed for female counselor at each garment factory to discuss the health problem and serve exact treatment immediately. We aim for improving health status of people. Common ailment, STDs, RTDs will be reduced and we will prevent vector borne, water borne, air and fecal borne diseases by giving essential preventive and curative health services. It is also important to develop a basic education department for creation of awareness in personal health and hygiene practices.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

There is no conflict of interest to be declared.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS:

All of authors contributed to this article equally. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

REFERENCES:

1. Rahman M, Rahman M. Sickness and Treatment: A Situation Analysis among the Garments Workers. AKMMCJ [Internet]. 6 Feb.2013 [cited 3 Nov. 2019]; 4(1):10-4. <https://www.banglajol.info/index.php/AKMMCJ/article/view/13678>
2. BGMEA Brushier, 2003, (page-14).
3. Accord on fire & safety in Bangladesh (bangladeshaccord.org)
4. M. Abul Kalam Azad, "A Health Care Initiative That Made a Difference in the Garment Factories of Bangladesh", Center for International Business Education, Ross School of Business, University of Michigan, Feb.2009.
5. Paul-Majumder, Pratima. "Health Status of the Garment Workers in Dhaka, Bangladesh": Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies.2003.
6. Zenija Roja, Valdis Kalkis, Inara Roja and Henrijs Kalkis "The effects of a medical hypnotherapy on clothing industry employees suffering from chronic pain"2013.
7. Dorothy D. Watts, M.P.H." The Relation of Patient Education to the Seeking of Medical Care". March 1964. Vol.56, No. 2.
8. R. S.F. Schilling. "Changing concepts in occupational health". Vol.59, No. 8, August 1969
9. Md. Golam Hasnain, Monjura Akter, Md. Shadab Ibn Sharafat, and Ayesha Mahmuda, "Morbidity patterns, nutritional status, and healthcare seeking behavior of female garment workers in Bangladesh". Published online 2014, May 10.
10. Jahan M.; Women Workers in Bangladesh Garments Industry; A Study of the Work Environment; International Journal of Social Science Tomorrow; Vol-1, No.3, Page No: 1-5
11. Rajat Das Gupta, Subrata Nag, Debashis Datta et.al. "Occupational Health Hazards among Workers in Garment Factories in Bangladesh: A Cross-Sectional Study". Developing Country studies ([www. I iste.org](http://www.iste.org)) ISSN 2224-607X (Paper) ISSN 2225-0565 (Online), Vol.5, No.5, 2015.
12. Aderonke O Akinpelu, Olufemi Oyeleye Oyewole, Adesola C Odole, Funmilayo D Ogunbamowo, "Work-related musculoskeletal pain and health-seeking behavior among Nigerian sewing machine operators". Tropical Journal of Medical Research. Year: 2016 | Volume: 19 | Issue: 2 | Page: 152-158
13. Akhter S., Salahuddin A.F.M, Iqbal M., Malek A.B.M.A., Jahan N.; Health and Occupational safety for female work force of garment industries in Bangladesh; Journal of Mechanical Engineering; Vol-ME 41 No.1, June 2010; Page: 65-70
14. Amr Jamal MD, SBFM, ABFM, MRCGP, MBI, Samina A Khan, Ahmed Al Humud, Abdulaziz Al-Duhyim, Mohammed Alrashed, Faisal Bin Shabr, Alwalid Alteraif, Abdullah Almuziri, Mowafa Househ, MEng, PhD, and Riaz Qureshi, "Association of Online Health Information–Seeking Behavior and Self-Care Activities Among Type 2 Diabetic Patients in Saudi Arabia", Published online 2015 Aug 12. doi: [10.2196/jmir.4312]